

EFFECTS OF RAMMING ON THE MOULD PROPERTIES OF YOLA NATURAL SAND.

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ABSTRACT

The paper has investigated the effects of ramming on the mould properties of Yola natural sand. The work considered the variation of the number of rams with green compression strength, dry compression strength, green permeability and bulk density. The results showed that as the number of rams increase, the green compression also increases attaining the highest strength of 186.17kPa as the number of rams reached 6 rams. The dry compression strength also increased with the number of rams. The green permeability however started increasing but dropped after the fourth blow. This drop is normal; after a certain level of compaction is attained the variation of number of rams with green permeability becomes inversely proportional. The number of rams' variation was directly proportional to the bulk density as the number of rams was increasing, the bulk density too was increasing, until the highest bulk density of 1.78g/cm³ was attained corresponding to 6 rams. The result of the investigation also revealed that the Yola natural sand have a clay content of 26%. The investigation has clearly shown that ramming has effect on the mould properties of Yola natural sand.

KEYWORDS: Effects, Ramming, Mould Properties and Yola natural sand.

INTRODUCTION

Sand casting is the commonest casting technique in Nigeria. All the 60 commercial foundries in Nigeria are based on sand casting technique (Ogo, *et al*, 2005). Nigeria is however, blessed with different types of sands and other raw materials needed for the foundry shops. These include clay deposits, coals, synthetic and natural sand just to mention a few (Atama *et al*, 2007, RMRDC, 1999, PD/CE NMDC 1999). Yola natural sand is located in Yola, Adamawa State of Nigeria. The sand does not require the addition of binder for preparing moulding mixtures for moulding in the foundry. The sand is used by local founders for moulding and casting of nonferrous metals and cast iron. Like most natural sands the natural sand has high clay content. The sand has had wide application because it saves the user the cost of buying clay binders. All that is required is the addition of water in the right proportion and proper mixing. Natural sand unlike synthetic sands requires the addition of clay binder and water for mould-mix preparation.

Foundry sands are not just ordinary sands we see here and there (Odetundun, 1993). They are sands with certain properties which made it useful for foundry application. There are various types of sands; these include silica (SiO₂) sand, which is classified into high silica sand, naturally bonded silica sand and synthetic silica sand. Others are special sands to which zircon, olivine, ilmenite, and chromite belong (Odetundun, 1993). These sands have different properties that made them applicable for different castings. As a result of that tests have to be carried-out on them to know exactly which of them is more applicable to a particular casting. Each type of casting requires sand with properties which vary according to the metal or alloy concerned and to the points most desired in the cast components. Since the properties of sand are crucial to the production of sound, dimensionally accurate castings, its selection and testing constitutes one of the vital steps in founding (Odetundun, 1993).

According to Beeley (1982) and Karl (2000) the degree of ramming during moulding operations influences moulding parameters and consequently affects the quality of castings produced. Newcombe *et al* (1993) developed a model which showed that binder, fines, and ramming force, all have an effect on erosion. Commenting on surface finish the researchers said that ramming was the only significant factor affecting surface finish. High ramming force produced a better finish. According to the researchers, soft ramming is a major cause of cracking and finning. Binder, fines and ramming are all significant effect, as well as a significant interaction between binder content and ramming force. According to Chakraborty and Dhindaw (1982) the degree of ramming affects such mould parameters as green, dry, baked compression strength, and shear strength, it also affects permeability, shatter index, bulk density and hardness.

The objective of this study is to critically study the effect of ramming on the mould properties of Yola natural sand. The study is to clearly draw conclusions on the best degree of ramming for quality moulds production for casting purpose.

MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY.

Materials.

The materials used for the work include; Yola natural sand sample from Yola, Adamawa State of Nigeria, water, and NaOH.

Equipment

The equipment used for the work were those of the National Metallurgical Development Centre, Jos Plateau State. These include specimen tube, pouring hope, specimen rammer, digital weighing balance, laboratory mixer, wash beakers, clay washer, electric permimeter, universal strength testing machine, and oven.

Experimental Procedure

Moulding mixture preparation.

The procedure for the work was to weigh 1kg of the natural sand using a digital weighing balance. It was then introduced into a laboratory size mixer for mulling. 4% water was added to the sand. The mixer which had an automatic timer, was adjusted to 5 minutes and the mixer was switched on. For all the moulding mixtures the timing was kept at 5 minutes, likewise the water was kept at 4%.

Compaction/ Ramming

After the preparation of the moulding mixture the moulding mixture was discharged into a plastic bucket with a cover and closed. Using a digital weighing balance and the specimen rammer, the actual amount for the preparation of standard specimen was determined. The amount was subsequently weighed into the specimen tube using the pouring hopper. The specimen tube was then transferred to the specimen rammer for the commencement of the compaction/ ramming test. Using the specimen rammer the number of rams was varied from 1- 6. In each case the specimen prepared were tested for green compression, dry compression strength, green permeability, and bulk density.

Green Compression Strength (GCS)

After subjecting the specimen to the stipulated number of rams as stated by the experimental design, the test specimen was ejected using the specimen ejecting plunger. It was then transferred to the universal strength testing machine to be failed in compression test using compression head accessories. The result was displayed on the green compression strength scale.

Dry Compression Strength (DCS)

The compacted specimens were removed from the specimen tube and air-dried for one day. They were then failed in compression using the universal strength testing machine. The result was displayed on the dry compression strength scale of the machine.

Green Permeability

The green permeability of the specimen was determined while they were still inside the specimen tube. The electric permimeter was used to determine the permeability of the specimen after ramming with the specimen rammer. The specimen tube containing the specimen was mounted on the electric permimeter and switch-on the test lever was adjusted to "test" and the reading displayed on the scale.

Bulk Density

The density measuring device on the specimen rammer was used to measure the bulk density of the specimen. Each specimen after ramming was tested for bulk density using the density indicator attached to the specimen rammer.

Clay Content Determination

The clay washer apparatus was used for the determination of the clay content of the Yola natural sand. The natural sand was washed using 3% NaOH solution prepared with distilled water. 50g of the sand was washed using the apparatus until it was clear. The sand was transferred unto a filtering paper, drained of water and dried in the oven at 105°C for 2 h. It was then removed, reweighed using a digital weighing balance. The difference between the initial weight and the final weight was multiplied by 2 to give the percentage clay content of the natural sand.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION
RESULTS

The result of the study has revealed that Yola natural sand has 26 % clay content. The effects of number of rams on sand mould parameters of Yola natural sand is displayed in figures 1-4. Plate 1 also shows some of the specimens produced during the test.

Figure 1: Effect of Number of Rams on the Green Compression Strength of Yola Natural Sand.

Figure 2: Effect of Number of Rams on the Dry Compression Strength of Yola Natural Sand.

Figure 3: Effect of Number of Rams on the Green Permeability.

Figure 4: Effect of Number of Rams on the Bulk Density

Plate I: Shows some of the Test Specimen Produced During the Test.

DISCUSSION

Green Compression Strength (GCS)

Figure 1 shows the effect of number of rams on green compression strength of Yola natural sand. The number of rams was increased from 1-6. The number “6” seems to be the upper limit for most works (Chakraborty and Dhindaw 1982, Heine *et al* 1967), however in a work carried out by Karl (2000) the number of rams was up to 13; it will be interesting to know how he handled the problem of measurement of green compression and other strengths with specimens far below standard dimension. From figure 1 it can be seen that as the number of rams is increasing the green compression strength too is increasing. Initially the increase is very slow; however, with the third ramming the increase became drastic. The figure showed a curve rising and assuming a near linear shape as the number of rams increased. As the degree of ramming increases the cohesion between the clay particles is reduced and hence the clay assists in better packing of the sand mixtures. Such packing, as well as formation of more electro-chemical bonds due to exposure to fresh surface charges during ramming, also results in increased green strength properties of the sand (Chakraborty and Dhindaw 1982, Richards 1982). This explanation quite fits the curve in figure 1 and agrees with the result of the test. The highest green compression strength of 186.17kPa corresponds to 6 rams.

Dry Compression Strength

The result of the study is shown in figure 2, which is the effect of number of rams on the dry compression strength of Yola natural sand. The increase in the dry strength of Yola natural sand was initially low as the number of rams were increased, just as in the case of green compression strength after the second ram there was a sudden drastic increase which continued until an optimum point was reached with 5 rams corresponding to a dry compression strength of 2923.48kPa, after which the dry compression strength dropped to 2826.95kPa. The drop may be attributed to the drastic reduction of the standard dimension of the test specimen or some distortion in the clay-water-sand bond. The shape of the curve in figure 2, clearly illustrate the variation of the number of rams with the dry compression strength. It has been explained that due to high degree of ramming (or high pressure) the cohesion between the clay particles is reduced and hence the clay assists in better packing of the sand mixtures resulting in high bulk density as well as high dry compression strength (Chakraborty and Dhindaw 1982, Nwajagu 1994). At the beginning of the ramming the cohesion between the clay particles is still high but as the ramming increases the cohesion is reduced giving way for better packing of the sand mixture, which is reflected in the high values of the dry compression strength.

Green Permeability

Figure 3, shows the effect of the number of rams on the green permeability of Yola natural sand. The figure showed that as the number of rams was increased the permeability was also increasing a value of 400 perm units was attained at 4 rams before the value of the permeability started decreasing as the number of rams were increased. The possible explanation to this behaviour could be that as the number of rams was increased the distance of air travel through the specimen was reduced, equally the ramming resulted in the reduction of cohesion between clay particles causing a rearrangement in the packing of the sand particles, more so, that there was no additional mixture to maintain the 50mm high standard specimen. The drop of permeability values at high number of rams is typical of number of rams versus permeability curves (Karl 2000, Ihom and Olubajo, 2002). The closing off of some of the through air passages may be possible.

This has been explained by several authors (Ihom and Olubajo 2002, Ihom *et al*, 2006, Mohammad *et al*, 2003). These authors explained that increasing the number of rams required to attain a 50mm high specimen results in dramatic decrease in permeability, an apparent result of the closing off of some of the continuous air passages.

Bulk Density

Figure 4, shows the effect of number of rams on bulk density of Yola natural sand. The figure showed a near linear curve the curve showed that as the number of rams is increasing the bulk density is also increasing. This behaviour is typical of most moulding sands the highest value of bulk density of 1.78g/cm³ occurred at 6 rams. For rigid moulds with high bulk density, high compaction and ramming is required (Rickards 1982, Mohammad *et al* 2003). Rigid mould with high bulk density reduces casting defects and contributes to sound casting (Chakraborty and Dhindaw 1982, Tokan *et al*, 2004). The intrinsic cohesion between the clay particles resists deformation of the clay-water mass in between the sand grains during ramming. Due to high degree of ramming the cohesion between the clay particles is reduced and hence the clay assists in better packing of the sand mixtures resulting in high bulk density as well as high dry compression strength (Karl 2000, Chakraborty and Dhindaw 1982, Tokan *et al* 2004).

CONCLUSIONS

The following conclusions have been drawn from the study:

1. The effects of ramming on moulding parameters of Yola natural sand have been investigated the results have shown that ramming affects mould parameters, such as green permeability, green compression strength, dry compression strength and bulk density.
2. As the degree of ramming increases the green compression strength also increases.
3. The dry compression strength increases with the degree of ramming.
4. The green permeability increases as the number of rams increases attaining a peak before dropping as the number of rams is increased.
5. The bulk density of the Yola natural sand increases with increased ramming.
6. The study has shown that Yola natural sand will have improved mould properties, if the sand is well compacted and rammed during moulding. The result of this improved mould properties will be sound castings.

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REFERENCES

- Atama, E.O., Aye, A.E., Yahaya, S. and Sunday, F.O. (2007): Possibility of using Locally Available Binders and Ochadamu Silica Sand for the Production of Foundry Cores, Proc. of NMS P139-140
- Beeley, P.R. (1982): Foundry Technology, Fourth Edition, Butterworth Scientific London, P141-155
- Chakraborty, M. and Dhindaw, B.K. (1982): Application of the Statistical Design of Experiments in the study of Clay Bonded Sand Mixtures, The British Foundryman, Journal of IBF, P114-117.
- Heine, R.W., Loper Jr. C.R., and Rosenthal, P.C. (1967): Principles of Metal Casting, 2nd Edition, McGraw-Hill, Inc P92-120.
- Ihom, A.P., Tuleun, L.T., and Anbua, E.E. (2006): The Effect of Common Salt on the Binding and Strength Properties of Bentonite in the Green State, Journal of Science and Technology Research, Vol.5. No.3, P95-97.

Ihom, A.P. and Olubajo, O.O. (2002): Determination of the Foundry Properties of Bende-Ameki Foundry Clay, Proc.of the NMS, P15-17.

Karl, B.R. (2000): Metal Casting, Reference Book for MY4130, Dept. of Materials Science and Engineering, Michigan Technology University, P11-16.

Mohammad, M.H., Bawa, M.A., and Akuchi, N.T. (2003): Characterization of Alkalari and Gombe Foundry Sand Samples, Proc. of the NMS, P31-33.

Newcombe, P.D., Whiting, L.V., Warda, R.W., Davis, K.G. (1993): Using Experimental Design to Investigate Sand-Related Castings Defects, AFS Transactions, 10:101-705.

Nwajagu, C.O. (1994): Foundry Theory and Practice, First Edition ABC Publishers Enugu, P92-120

.Odetundun, E.B.(1993): Sand Testing, a Manual for Sand Testing in NMDC Sand Testing Laboratory, P1-10.

Ogo, D.U.I, Ette, A.O. and Nnuka, E.E. (2005): Agricultural Mechanization in Nigeria: The Role of the Foundries, Proc. of NMS, P15-18.

P/CE NMDC (1999): Research and Development Efforts at NMDC Jos towards Arresting the Declining Fortunes of the Nigerian Metallurgical Industry, Proc.of the NMS, P17-28.

Rickards, P.J. (1982): Factors Affecting the Soundness and Dimensions of Iron Castings made in Cold-Curing Chemically Bonded Sand Moulds, The British Foundryman, Journal of IBF, P213-214.

RMRDC (1999): Technical Brief on Minerals In Nigeria (Bentonite), ISBN 978-2043-49-4, P2-10.

Tokan, A., Adelemoni, A.A. and Datau, S.G. (2004): Mould Characteristics of Azare Foundry Sand JORMAR Vol.No.1, ISSN 1597-3204, 67-70.

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